

THE INFLAMMATORY RESPONSE TO EXERCISE IN SPINAL CORD INJURED INDIVIDUALS – THE INFLUENCE OF AUTONOMIC FUNCTION

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Abstract The acute inflammatory response to exercise is attenuated in individuals with a cervical spinal cord injury (SCI), possibly related to the autonomic dysfunction resulting in the impaired sympathetic innervation below the lesion. **Purpose** This study investigates the influence of autonomic function on the acute inflammatory response to endurance exercise in people with SCI using exercise-induced as well as resting measures of autonomic function. **Methods** Seventeen wheelchair athletes with a cervical SCI (CSCI, N=7) and without a cervical SCI (NON-CSCI, N=10) participated in a wheelchair half-marathon. Blood was taken prior, post and 1 h post-race to determine serum concentrations of adrenaline and noradrenaline as measures of autonomic function and interleukin-6 (IL-6) as a measure of the inflammatory response to exercise. Supine blood pressure and heart rate variability were measured to assess autonomic function at rest. **Results** CSCI showed a lower ratio of the low and high frequency power of the variability in RR intervals (LF/HF RRI, $p=0.038$) and low frequency power of the systolic blood pressure variability (LF SBP, $p=0.005$) compared to NON-CSCI. Following the race, catecholamine concentrations increased only in NON-CSCI ($p<0.036$). The increase in IL-6 post-race was larger in NON-CSCI ($p=0.040$). Post-race catecholamine levels explained 60% of the variance in the IL-6 response ($r=0.77$, $p=0.040$), which was further increased when LF/HF RRI and LF SBP were added to the regression model ($R^2=81\%$, $p=0.012$). **Conclusion** Post-exercise plasma catecholamine concentrations and the autonomic function measures at rest revealed impaired autonomic function in CSCI, which was strongly associated with the attenuated IL-6 response to exercise in this group. Therefore, the autonomic dysfunction present in individuals with a cervical SCI may make exercise less effective in preventing chronic low-grade inflammation in this population.

Keywords Interleukin-6, Heat shock protein 72, Wheelchair racing, Upper-body exercise, Sympathetic response, Adrenaline

Introduction

Chronic low-grade inflammation, characterised by elevated resting levels of pro-inflammatory proteins (e.g. interleukin-6 (IL-6) and extracellular heat shock protein 72 (eHsp72)) and strongly associated with chronic diseases such as type 2 diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease, is more prevalent in people with a spinal cord injury (SCI) compared with members of the able-bodied population (Bauman and Spungen 2008). Regular exercise, partly mediated by the acute increase in inflammatory markers such as IL-6 following each session, can improve the

inflammatory profile at rest (Petersen and Pedersen 2005). However, the acute inflammatory response to exercise is attenuated in people with a cervical spinal cord injury (CSCI), possibly related to a reduced active muscle mass or autonomic dysfunction (Paulson, Goosey-Tolfrey et al. 2013). This study investigates the association between autonomic function indices, measured at rest and in response to exercise, with the acute inflammatory response to a wheelchair half-marathon.

Methods

Participants

Participants were 17 male recreational wheelchair athletes with CSCI (N=7) or without CSCI (NON-CSCI, N=10), the latter group including individuals with a spinal lesion below the cervical level (N=6), spina bifida (N=2), polio (N=1) and myotonia congenita (N=1). Participants took part in the wheelchair half-marathon of Oita 2016.

Autonomic function at rest

One to two days prior to the race, a sit-up tilt test was conducted in 16 of the 17 athletes for the assessment of autonomic function. Participants were rested for 5 min in a supine position and were then elevated into the sitting position, which they maintained for another 5 min. The following blood pressure and heart rate variability measures assessed in the supine position were included as autonomic function indices, based on Claydon and Krassioukov (2008): the ratio of the power in the low (0.07 – 0.20 Hz) and high frequency (power = 0.20 – 35 Hz) domain of the heart rate variability (LF/HF RRI), total power and power in the low frequency domain of systolic blood pressure variability (TP SBP and LF SBP, respectively).

Wheelchair half-marathon

Blood was drawn from an antecubital vein pre, immediately post and 1 h post-race for the assessment of plasma adrenaline and noradrenaline (i.e. autonomic function indices in response to exercise), as well as serum IL-6 and eHsp72 concentrations.

Statistical analyses

Data are presented as mean±SD. Potential differences between CSCI and NON-CSCI in outcome measures assessed at rest were tested using independent T-tests, while repeated measures ANOVAs were used to assess acute responses to the race. To further evaluate the association between autonomic function and the acute inflammatory response to exercise, (multiple) linear regression was performed including all participants, with post-race IL-6 as the independent variable.

Results

LF/HF RRI ($p=0.038$), LF SBP ($p=0.005$) and TP SBP ($p<0.001$) were smaller in CSCI compared with NON-CSCI. In addition, CSCI had lower resting plasma concentrations of adrenaline and noradrenaline ($p<0.001$). Following the race, plasma adrenaline and noradrenaline concentrations were increased in NON-CSCI only ($p<0.036$). Although elevated in both groups ($p<0.033$), the increase in serum IL-6 concentrations in response to the race was larger in NON-CSCI compared with CSCI ($p=0.040$). Serum eHsp72 following the race was elevated in neither of both groups ($p>0.391$) (Fig. 1).

Catecholamines (adrenaline and noradrenaline) together explained 60% of the variance in post-race IL-6 concentrations ($p=0.04$). Although the autonomic function indices assessed at rest (i.e. LF/HF RRI, TP SPB and LF SBP) did not explain a significant portion of the variance in IL-6 when used in isolation ($p>0.08$), the addition of LF/HF and one of the two blood pressure variability measures to the model with the catecholamines increased the explained variance in post-race IL-6 from 60% to $>81%$ ($p<0.012$).

Figure 1. Changes in circulating concentrations of IL-6, eHsp72, adrenaline and noradrenaline in response to the wheelchair half-marathon. Lines represent the individual responses, while bars represent the group mean. * Significant difference between pre- and post-race. ^ Significant time x group interaction between NON-CSCI and CSCI ($p<0.05$).

Conclusion and discussion

The dampened acute inflammatory response to a wheelchair half-marathon in CSCI was strongly associated with the autonomic dysfunction found in this group. This may make exercise less effective in reducing chronic low-grade inflammation in members of this population. Taking a wide range of factors associated with autonomic dysfunction into account may hence be of use to inform health promoting strategies to reduce chronic low-grade inflammation in individuals with CSCI.

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